

A Cryptographic Protocol to Secure Communications in Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Environments

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Abstract. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are increasingly deployed across a wide range of applications, including military surveillance, environmental monitoring, and disaster management. Typically, UAVs are remotely operated from ground control stations (GCS), but as their roles expand, their communication requirements grow in complexity. Beyond basic flight control commands, advanced missions may involve UAV-to-UAV communication to support collaborative tasks or swarming behaviours. Given the critical nature of many of these applications, the underlying communication protocols are potential targets for cyberattacks. In this work, we propose a communication framework aimed at enhancing the security of UAV systems by combining both symmetric and public-key cryptography.

Keywords: Unmanned Aerial Vehicles · Drones · Security · Protocol · Cryptography · Ubiquitous Computing.

1 Introduction

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), commonly known as drones, have emerged as transformative ubiquitous technologies across civilian, commercial, and military applications. Their capacity to operate in inaccessible or hazardous environments, gather high-resolution data in real time, and perform (semi-)autonomous missions makes them indispensable in domains ranging from precision agriculture, infrastructure inspection, and disaster response to package delivery, aerial photography, and surveillance [1]. With the increasing integration of UAVs into national airspaces and interconnected digital infrastructures, ensuring the reliability and security of their communications has become a paramount concern.

Despite their growing importance, UAV systems rely on resource-constrained onboard hardware and wireless communication channels for control, telemetry,

and data transmission. These links are inherently vulnerable to cyberthreats, including eavesdropping, jamming, spoofing, and unauthorised control [4]. Such attacks can lead to serious consequences, ranging from data theft and privacy violations to loss of control, mission failure, or even physical harm. Therefore, ensuring robust and resilient communication security, both between UAVs (UAV-to-UAV) and between Ground Control Station and UAVs (GCS-to-UAV), is crucial for the trustworthy deployment of UAV applications. In this context, the adoption of cryptography is crucial to ensure the confidentiality and authenticity of transmitted messages while accommodating the stringent computational and energy constraints of UAV environments. This paper presents two protocols designed to enhance the security of UAV communications using cryptography. The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 reviews background on UAV security protocols, Section 3 describes the system architecture, Section 4 details the proposed security protocols, Section 5 discusses their effectiveness and feasibility across UAV environments, and Section 6 closes the article.

2 Background

Securing communications in UAV systems has become a central focus of research in recent years [8]. Despite growing awareness, many core technologies integrated into aviation and UAV platforms still lack built-in security. A notable example is Automatic Dependent Surveillance–Broadcast (ADS-B), a widely adopted surveillance protocol that periodically broadcasts GPS-related data such as position and velocity. Although effective for tracking and situational awareness, ADS-B was not designed with encryption or authentication capabilities, exposing it to eavesdropping or spoofing [6]. To secure communication channels, [2] proposes the symmetric encryption-based one-time pad (OTP), which offers strong security by combining the plaintext with a random key of equal length. However, its practical use is limited by key management challenges: the key must match the size of the message, be used only once, and be securely pre-distributed, an issue particularly problematic in bandwidth-limited or dynamic UAV networks. Asymmetric cryptography, on the other hand, presents significant challenges in UAV environments: (i) public-key operations (especially modular exponentiation and elliptic curve arithmetic) are computationally intensive [3], and (ii) the need for a secure and reliable infrastructure for key/certificate issuance, distribution, and revocation [7]. Ultimately, secure communications are essential not only for operational reliability but also for preserving privacy in such increasingly interconnected UAV networks [9].

3 Architecture

Our scenario consists of multiple UAVs and a GCS, all interconnected through a wireless network (see Fig. 1). This network can be enabled through Wi-Fi technology offering extended outdoor coverage, *e.g.*, around 250 m under 802.11n, or up to 1 km under the IoT-oriented 802.11ah.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed system.

Each UAV is equipped with a set of onboard sensors responsible for monitoring aviation parameters and motor status, along with a base system and a dedicated flight control system that manages navigation, stability, and the coordination of aerial movement. Additionally, each UAV incorporates a computing unit (*e.g.*, a Raspberry Pi) for executing onboard services, including image processing and other UAV-specific tasks. Communication capabilities are supported through a wireless communication link that enables bidirectional data exchange with other UAVs and with the GCS. The GCS conducts mission planning, telemetry, and fleet coordination, and is supported by a Ground Control Back End, where a so-called Trusted Administrator manages the system’s security policies.

The system assumes full communication visibility across all nodes, *i.e.*, both UAV-to-UAV and GCS-to-UAV communications. Message exchanges are designed to be lightweight and efficient, typically consisting of short packets (less than 1500 bytes) and using UDP as transport protocol to minimise latency and avoid the retransmission delays associated with TCP.

4 Secure Communication Protocols

We propose two communication protocols, each of them related to a type of communication: (i) GCS-to-UAV, where the GCS initiates communication with a UAV, and (ii) UAV-to-UAV, a peer-to-peer channel between UAVs. Both protocols follow a two-phase design: an *initialisation phase*, which employs public-key cryptography for secure key exchange and authentication, and a *communication phase*, which relies on symmetric cryptography to ensure efficiency and low computational overhead during subsequent message exchanges. This hybrid cryptographic approach combines the strengths of asymmetric and symmetric encryption, achieving both security and performance. In these protocols, we assume that: (i) the GCS is fully trustworthy, (ii) adversaries have gained access to the wireless network and are able to eavesdrop, modify, or replay messages

on the network, and (iii) all nodes possess a public-private (pk, sk) key pair and the Trusted Administrator pre-distributes these keys.

For the sake of simplicity, both protocols are described over a toy example system composed of a GCS and two UAVs: UAV1 and UAV2. In this context, the GCS holds $\{\text{GCS}_{\text{sk}}, \text{UAV1}_{\text{pk}}, \text{UAV2}_{\text{pk}}\}$, the UAV1 holds $\{\text{UAV1}_{\text{sk}}, \text{GCS}_{\text{pk}}\}$, and the UAV2 holds $\{\text{UAV2}_{\text{sk}}, \text{GCS}_{\text{pk}}\}$.

4.1 Protocol 1: GCS-to-UAV Communication

Initialisation phase. The GCS aims at sending message m and hence initiates communication with a UAV (*e.g.*, UAV1). The GCS generates a fresh sequence number n to prevent replay attacks, and a random symmetric session key k , which will be used to protect subsequent messages during the communication phase. The GCS then constructs the payload $m' = \text{Enc}_{\text{UAV1}_{\text{pk}}}(n \parallel k \parallel m)$. This encrypted payload is signed using GCS_{sk} , producing $s = \text{Sig}_{\text{GCS}_{\text{sk}}}(m')$. The resulting packet $\{m', s\}$ is transmitted to UAV1 over UDP. Upon receiving the packet, UAV1 verifies the signature s using GCS_{pk} . If the signature is valid, UAV1 authenticates the sender as the legitimate GCS, and proceeds to decrypt m' using UAV1_{sk} , thereby recovering the session key k , the sequence number n , and the message m . UAV1 also checks that n has not been previously used to prevent replay attacks.

Communication phase. From this point onward, if more packets are to be sent, both entities begin the communication phase using symmetric cryptography. For example, if UAV1 sends a message m_i to the GCS, UAV1 prepends a sequence number $n + i$ and encrypts the result using the session key k : $m'_i = \text{Enc}_k(n + i \parallel m_i)$. Then, it computes a hashed message authentication code (HMAC) for integrity and authenticity: $h = \text{HMAC}_k(m'_i)$. UAV1 then transmits the packet $\{m'_i, h\}$ to the GCS via UDP. Upon reception, the GCS verifies the message by checking the HMAC h using the shared session key k . If the authentication succeeds, it decrypts m'_i to recover the original message m_i and the associated sequence number. A message is discarded if its sequence number is lower than the last accepted one. This procedure is analogous when the GCS sends messages to UAV1.

4.2 Protocol 2: UAV-to-UAV Communication

Initialisation phase. When a specific UAV intends to communicate with another UAV, the initiating UAV must first request authorisation and a session key from the GCS before direct communication can occur. Suppose UAV1 intends to initiate communication with UAV2, and plans to send up to p messages. UAV1 constructs a request message $r = \{1, 2, p\}$, indicating the source and destination UAV identifiers and the permitted message count. To ensure confidentiality and authenticity, the request is encrypted with the GCS's public key, $r' = \text{Enc}_{\text{GCS}_{\text{pk}}}(r)$, and then signed using UAV1's private key, $s = \text{Sig}_{\text{UAV1}_{\text{sk}}}(r')$. The resulting packet $\{r', s\}$ is sent to the GCS via UDP. Upon receiving the packet, the GCS verifies the signature s using UAV1_{pk} and decrypts r' with GCS_{sk}

to recover the original request r . If the request is valid and UAV1 is authorised to communicate with UAV2 for up to p messages, the GCS generates a symmetric session key k_{12} . The GCS then prepares the corresponding payloads to securely distribute the session key to both UAVs. For UAV1: $m'_1 = \text{Enc}_{\text{UAV1}_{\text{pk}}}(k_{12})$, $s_1 = \text{Sig}_{\text{GCS}_{\text{sk}}}(m'_1)$; and for UAV2: $m'_2 = \text{Enc}_{\text{UAV2}_{\text{pk}}}(k_{12})$, $s_2 = \text{Sig}_{\text{GCS}_{\text{sk}}}(m'_2)$. The GCS sends the packets $\{m'_1, s_1\}$ and $\{m'_2, s_2\}$ to UAV1 and UAV2, respectively. Upon reception, each UAV verifies the digital signature using GCS_{pk} and decrypts the encrypted payload using its own private key to retrieve the session key k_{12} . With the shared key established, UAV1 and UAV2 can now exchange up to p messages directly using symmetric cryptography.

Communication phase. After this initialisation, each message m transmitted from one UAV to the other includes a fresh sequence number n to prevent replay attacks. The message is first encrypted, $m' = \text{Enc}_{k_{12}}(n || m)$, and then authenticated with an HMAC code, $h = \text{HMAC}_{k_{12}}(m')$. The transmitting UAV sends the packet $\{m', h\}$ via UDP. Upon reception, the receiving UAV verifies the HMAC using the shared key k_{12} . If verification succeeds, it decrypts the message and checks the freshness of the sequence number, discarding messages with repeated or outdated identifiers. Although the protocol above describes communication between two UAVs, the protocol is scalable to support communication among an arbitrary number of UAVs. In such cases, the initiating UAV specifies the list of UAVs it intends to communicate with, and the GCS responds by generating a shared group key and securely distributing it to all involved UAVs.

5 Discussion

The proposed communication protocols effectively enforce security properties required in adversarial UAV networks. Confidentiality is ensured through encryption: public-key cryptography during the initialisation phase and symmetric-key cryptography during the communication phase. Thus, intruders eavesdropping the network are unable to access the message contents. Integrity and authenticity are achieved via digital signatures and HMACs, allowing message receivers to verify that data has not been tampered with and originates from a legitimate sender. Replay protection is provided through the use of sequence numbers, which prevents attackers from reusing previously valid messages.

In addition to their security guarantees, the proposed protocols are designed with practical feasibility in mind. By limiting computationally intensive operations (*e.g.*, public-key cryptography) to the initialisation phase and relying on symmetric encryption for subsequent exchanges, the protocols reduce both computational and energy overhead, extending the battery life of computing units running on Raspberry Pi. The protocol logic can be efficiently implemented using lightweight cryptographic libraries such as mbedTLS [5], which offer optimised support for essential cryptographic primitives. Furthermore, designating the Ground Control Back End as a central authority for key management, under the supervision of the Trusted Administrator, ensures that only authorised communication occurs.

6 Conclusions

UAVs are increasingly being used in coordinated missions, where secure communication is critical. In this paper, we have proposed two protocols for GCS-to-UAV and UAV-to-UAV communication, combining asymmetric and symmetric cryptography to ensure secure and efficient data exchange, even on resource-constrained devices with limited computational and energy capacities. Future work will explore support for larger payloads requiring more than one transmission packet (*e.g.*, images) and enhance reliability over error-prone wireless links.

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References

1. Ahmed, F., et al.: Recent Advances in Unmanned Aerial Vehicles: A Review. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering* **47**(7), 7963–7984 (2022)
2. Atoev, S., et al.: The Secure UAV Communication Link Based on OTP Encryption Technique. In: *Proc. 11th International Conference on Ubiquitous and Future Networks*. pp. 1–3. IEEE, Zagreb, Croatia (2019)
3. Haque, M.S., et al.: A New Cyber Security Framework Towards Secure Data Communication for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV). In: *Security and Privacy in Communication Networks, LNICST*, vol. 239, pp. 113–122. Springer, Cham (2017)
4. Mantas, E., et al.: Who watches the new watchmen? The challenges for drone digital forensics investigations. *Array* **14**, 100135 (2022)
5. Mbed TLS: An open-source SSL/TLS library (2024), <https://github.com/Mbed-TLS/mbedtls>
6. Pan, W.J., et al.: ADS-B Data Authentication Based on ECC and X. 509 Certificate. *Journal of Electronic Science and Technology* **10**(1), 51–55 (2012)
7. Sahingoz, O.K.: Multi-Level Dynamic Key Management for Scalable Wireless Sensor Networks with UAV. In: *Ubiquitous Information Technologies and Applications, LNEE*, vol. 214, pp. 11–19. Springer, Dordrecht (2013)
8. Shafique, A., et al.: Survey of Security Protocols and Vulnerabilities in Unmanned Aerial Vehicles. *IEEE Access* **9**, 46927–46948 (2021)
9. Solanas, A., et al.: Privacy-Oriented Analysis of Ubiquitous Computing Systems: A 5-D Approach. In: *Security of Ubiquitous Computing Systems*, pp. 201–213. Springer, Cham (2021)